

V International Forum on Teacher Education

Comparative Study of Social and Professional Values of Modern Teachers with Various Pedagogical Experience (the Case of Russia and Belarus)

Albina R. Drozdikova-Zaripova (a) *, Natalya N. Kalatskaya (a), Maria Zhigalova (b)

(a) Kazan (Volga region) federal university, 42000 Kazan, Kremlevskaya str. 18, Russia
(b) Brest State Technical University, Brest, Belarus

Abstract

The paper investigated the changing system of values and value orientations of teachers belonging to different generations and cultures in the context of variability in globalization processes. The paper is aimed to identify cross-cultural features of social-professional values and value orientations of Russian and Belarusian teachers divided into three groups in compliance with their pedagogical experience and phases of professional development (from 0 to 5 years - a young teacher, from 6 to 20 years - a teacher - professional, and in case of more than 20 years - a teacher - expert). The leading research methods are questionnaires, experiment and comparison. Student's t-test, concordance coefficient and correlation analyses were applied to conduct statistical processing of research results. The study recruited 118 Russian secondary school teachers in the Republic of Tatarstan and 160 teachers of Brest region in the Republic of Belarus.

It has been revealed that the value sphere of Belarusian teachers throughout their professional development is less subject to change in comparison with Russian teachers. We found out that both in Russian and Belarusian samples, teachers with various teaching experience mostly implement spiritual and moral values. Russian and Belarusian teachers are focused on displaying their decency throughout their professional career. Health and Happy Family Life refer to key values of teachers in two cultures regardless of the length of their professional experience. The structure of value sphere in Russian and Belarusian teachers with different teaching experience has its own specificity.

Obtained results enabled to determine promising areas of highly qualified teachers' training and retraining for work in modern multicultural educational systems.

* Albina R. Drozdikova-Zaripova Tel.: 89053118397
E-mail address: bina1976@rambler.ru

Keywords: culture; social values; professional values; personal values; spiritual-moral values; values of life; civil values; intellectual values; value orientations; teachers.

© 2019 Albina R. Drozdikova-Zaripova, Natalya N. Kalatskaya, Maria Zhigalova

This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Published by Kazan Federal University and peer-reviewed under responsibility of IFTE-2019 (V International Forum on Teacher Education)

Introduction

In the post-Soviet space, the vector of needs development in the society and the individual changes due to social shifts that occur during transitional periods of social development. Requirements for teachers' professional competencies are revised; they predetermine value transformation in the teacher as a carrier and regulator of society's material and spiritual culture, and universal values as well.

At present, teacher's value sphere is increasingly becoming the subject of serious scientific, sociological, cultural, psychological and pedagogical studies as in the context of active migration there is an opportunity to select experts of different ethnic statuses and different levels of mastering social and professional values. It is obvious that this level depends largely on expert's competitiveness, their success in society and the quality of performed work.

While society faces global challenges, modern science does not give sufficient consideration to the changing system of teacher's values in different generations as the foundation of teachers' training for work in specific multicultural educational environment.

Problem Statement

The issue of personality's values and value orientations is investigated in works of Russian sociologists, philosophers and psychologists: M.I. Bobneva (1978), O.G. Drobnitsky (2002), O.A. Tyrnova (2010) et al.

L.I. Barbashova (2009), V.I. Andreyev (2012), A.R. Drozdikova-Zaripova and N.N. Kalatskaya (2016) et al., considered problems of pedagogical values formation and functioning in the teacher.

The specificity of future vocational teachers' social-professional values formation studied by A.I. Trotskaya's (2015) in her thesis is of great interest for the present research.

The issue of teacher's values in their various aspects is presented in foreign researches.

Authors examine the impact of value orientations on interaction and cooperation of the teaching staff (Ning & Lee, 2015); the relationship between professional values and critical thinking of math teachers and IT teachers working in secondary school (Şahin, Tunca, etc., 2016); dominant value orientations of Kazakh teachers (Ilimkhanova, Perlenbetov, Tazhbayeva, etc., 2014), etc.

W. Veugelers (2010) considers teachers' moral values and emphasizes that they intertwine all aspects of teaching: curricula, school culture and teachers' moral behavior as well. Training of students -

future teachers assumes acquaintance with moral values and their meanings. Teachers have to develop sensitivity in themselves to critically estimate their behavior and determine moral values necessary to correct and develop.

Y. Fisher (2013) devoted the research to studying professional ethics and values of Israeli teachers. Teachers' moral educational behavior was studied as the combination of three groups of values: universal values - values recognized in most modern societies; social values (including family) values which are under the influence of universal values; personal values – individual's characteristic when he / she is perceived as a certain uniqueness.

T. Tselikkaya, S. Phyloglu (2014) paid much attention to content study of such concepts as "values" and "education values".

The role of value on teachers' internalization of external barriers and externalization of personal beliefs for classroom technology integration is considered in the study of V.W. Vongkulluksn, K. Xie & M.A. Bowman (2018). The authors show that teachers' valuable beliefs concerning technologies influence the way they acquire actual access to technologies and integrate technologies in class, in general. It has been revealed that teachers' valuable beliefs impact the interrelation between obtained support at external barriers emergence and their practice of integration in class.

Research Questions

Psychology and pedagogy has not yet given an accurate conceptual differentiation between the concepts "valuable orientations" and "values".

According to E.F. Zeer's (2008) opinion, analyses of the expert's personality of this or that profession, his/her attitude to the world are impossible without studying the system of their valuable orientations as central personality's formations. Valuable orientations express person's conscientious attitude to social reality and specify behavior motivation significantly influencing all sides of professional activity. The structure of personality valuable orientations, combination and degree of preference concerning other values enable to define goals that person's professional activity is directed to.

Values of professional and pedagogical activity as the subject of our consideration are of special interest for us. Internal, emotionally mastered regulator of teacher's activity determining their attitude to the world around and to themselves as well as modeling contents and nature of performing professional activity are regarded as teacher's values (Petukhova, 2013).

Some scientists distinguish pedagogical values according to the level of their existence that, therefore, may become the foundation for their classification.

I.F. Isaev (2004) Investigates issues of pedagogical values and their classification and builds the following hierarchy of values: social-pedagogical, professional-group and personal-pedagogical.

E.N. Shiyanov (1991) proposed to divide pedagogical values and regard teachers' material, spiritual and public needs as the foundation for classification: values aimed to realize personality in social and professional environment; values to meet teacher's need to communicate; values to develop creative identity; values to promote self-realization; values to satisfy utilitarian-pragmatic demand.

Classification of values proposed by Z.I. Ravkin deserves consideration (1995). He brought out socio-political values; intellectual values; moral values; values of professional and pedagogical activity. Some other scientists consider social-pedagogical aspect based on pedagogical activity inclusion into the structure of society and social relationships as the foundation of classification. In this regard, the authors

specify public-pedagogical, professional-group and individual-personal values (Korotayeva& Matveychuk, 2012).

Though teacher's valuable sphere has attracted interest of many researchers, there are significantly fewer publications that reveal researcher's experience to identify teachers' social-professional values as sustainable motivational and meaningful formations in the context of teacher's successful pedagogical activity and professional development; there are almost no researches on the problem when it comes to consideration of teachers with various pedagogical experience.

In our research, teachers' social and professional values are assumed as a dialectic unity of social, professional and personal values which constitute the basis of teachers' cultural and professional competences. The structure of social-professional values uncludes: spiritual-moral, life, civil, intellectual and professional values. Social-professional values are those guidelines on the basis of which the person chooses, masters and performs professional activity. These are also means providing personal socially important result of pedagogical activity. Social-professional values are included into the structure of teacher's personality; they are implied as the base of teacher's orientation and world outlook position as well as social-professional development.

Present day teachers' social-professional values are of interest as considerable shifts have occurred in the value system of citizens within the Post-Soviet period over the last two decades. However, changes in the system of teachers' s values may differ from those that the society establishes in general. It is possible to assume that values of teachers who got professional education at the end of the Soviet period and, therefore, have obtained profound pedagogical experience are less subjected to changes. At the same time, the teacher's personality as an example to follow, his/her mastering these or those life and professional values determine students' motivation for life-long learning so as to play a key role in economic and social life of the country and its social arrangement in the near future. In many respects this choice depends on purposes and values that the youth of today are guided by and on their social - psychological and moral readiness.

This problem is especially urgent and significant for sovereign states of Russia and Belarus in the territory of which the uniform migration space has been created, and citizens have got common opportunities to obtain free tuition and employment.

Hence, one may infer that the study of social-professional values of teachers with different teaching experience, their correlation with values prevailing in society can provide the clue to understand psychological problems experienced by the teacher of today and their willingness to work in modern multicultural educational systems to build an adequate psychological support of pedagogical activity.

Purpose of the Study

The goal of the research is to reveal cross-cultural features of social-professional values and value orientations of teachers in Russia and the Republic of Belarus divided into three groups in compliance with their pedagogical experience and phases of professional development (from 0 to 5 years - a young teacher, from 6 to 20 years – a teacher - professional, and in case of more than 20 years - a teacher- expert).

Research Methods

The Methodology and Empirical Methods

Experimental work aimed to study regularities of teachers' valuable sphere formation was implemented according to the technique "Diagnostics of social and professional values of the teacher" elaborated by the authors (Drozdikova-Zaripova A.R., Kalatskaya N.N.); 118 Russian secondary school teachers (from the Republic of Tatarstan) and 160 teachers from Brest region of the Republic of Belarus participated in the research.

The questionnaire consists of two lists of values: terminal and instrumental; they are assessed on a 7-score scale (on the scale from 5 to 1 score). Stimulant material for each part of the questionnaire is represented by a set of 40 values. As for the first list of values (terminal), the importance of each value is assessed as the guiding principle in respondents' life; according to the second list (instrumental), values are evaluated due to the degree of their greatest realization in the life of each subject (value orientations). Lists of values are constructed in compliance with the following principle: each value corresponding to a specific type of values alternates in a strictly defined sequence (spiritual, moral, life, civil, intellectual and professional values); as a result, all 40 values can be grouped into five types of values and each group of values consists of 8 values. Results are processed by calculating average scores for each type of value (list 1) and value orientations (list 2) that show the degree of their significance for the testee in accordance with the scale of assessment.

Experiment

Such indicators as participants' age, their gender, pedagogical experience and nationality (Table 1) have been defined by the questionnaire of the participant.

Table 1. Social-professional data of study participants (in %)

Indicators	Gender		Age (years)				Pedagogical experience	
	em.	ale.	30	1-45	6-55	>55	0-5	>20
Russia				1				
Belarus	3.2	.8	8.6	7.1	0.7	3.6	8.6	8.6
				1				
	5	5	0.6	4.4	6.9	.1	1.9	3.1

Table 2 and Table 3 provide distribution results of values types in teachers from the two countries, with their pedagogical experience in view.

Table 2. Distribution of types of values in Russian teachers with different teaching experience (ranks, scores)

Pedagogical experience (years)	Types of values					
	Spiritual-moral	Spiritual	Life	Civil	Intellectual	Professional
0-5	III (3.38* ±0.69)	II (3.52 ±0.69)	IV (3.27* ±0.37)	V (3.12* ±0.53)	I (3.6 ±0.37)	
6-20	I (3.89* ±0.36)	III (3.73±0.5 7) ±0.34)	IV (3.74* ±0.36)	V (3.49* ±0.36)	II (3.78 ±0.28)	
>20	I (3.7 ±0.35)	II (3.59±0.6 5) ±0.31)	V (3.35 ±0.37)	IV (3.42 ±0.37)	III (3.52 ±0.29)	

Designation: * $p \leq 0.05$ (differences in mean values according to Student's t-test: on the scale of spiritual-moral values - $t_{emp} = 2.49$, on the scale of civil values - $t_{emp} = 2.13$, and intellectual values - $t_{emp} = 2.05$).

Table 3. Distribution of types of values in Belarusian teachers with different teaching experience (ranks, scores)

Pedagogical experience (years)	Types of values					
	Spiritual-moral	Spiritual	Life	Civil	Intellectual	Professional
0-5	I (3.58 ±0.55)	II (3.52 ±0.36)	IV (3.42 ±0.52)	V (3.19 ±0.39)	III (3.44 ±0.28)	
6-20	I (3.68 ±0.41)	II (3.62±0.3 6) ±0.47)	III (3.54 ±0.47)	V (3.31 ±0.54)	IV (3.53 ±0.47)	
>20	I (3.73 ±0.5)	II (3.74±0.3 8) ±0.83)	III (3.58 ±0.63)	V (3.34 ±0.63)	IV (3.57 ±0.61)	

Young Russian teachers specified such values as Health (4.45 scores out of maximum 5 scores), Kindness (4.18 scores), Happiness (4.18 scores), Happy Family Life and Professional pedagogical ideals (4 scores per each) as the most significant values for guiding principles in their lives; Belarusian teachers identified Happy family life (4.5 scores) and Health (physical and mental) (4.25 scores).

Russian teachers having pedagogical experience from 6 to 20 years pointed out the following

values (in scores): Health (4.45), Peaceful life (4.45), Kindness (4.36), Inner harmony (4.27) and Happy Family Life (4.2) as the most significant values in their lives; as for teachers from Belarus they are as follows: Health (4.4), Happiness (4.33), Happy family life (4.23).

Teachers with teaching experience over 20 years in the Russian Federation referred (in scores) Health (4.48), Kindness (4.23), Happy Family Life (4.22), Happiness (4.03), and Peaceful Life (3.97) to dominant values; in Belarus they are Health (4.58), Peaceful life (4.48), Happy family life (4.37) and Professional pedagogical ideals (4.3).

Values that are less important for teachers with the experience up to 5 years include (in scores) : in Russia - Spiritual life (2.27), Intellectual property (2.36), Public recognition (2.45) and Intellect (2.5); in Belarus - Public Recognition (2.38), Political Freedom and Intuition (2.75 each); Public recognition (2.55), Science (3), Intellectual property (3.09), Innovation and Creativity (3.27) are less significant for Russian teachers - professionals (work experience from 6 to 20 years) compared to Belarusian teachers' values such as Public recognition (2.14) and Intellectual property (2.68); Russian teachers - experts do not regard Public recognition (2.44), Intellectual property (2.86), Science (2.89) and National sovereignty (2.92) as life values though Belarusian teachers-experts refer Authority (2.58), Public recognition (2.67) and Intellectual property (2.72) to this category of values.

Table 4 and Table5 show distribution results according to types of value orientations (instrumental social-professional values) in Russian and Belarusian teachers having various teaching experience.

Table 4. Distribution of types of value orientations in Russian teachers with different teaching experience (ranks, scores)

Pedagogical experience (years)	Types of value orientations					
	Spiritual-moral	Life	Civil	Intellectual	Professional	Profes
0-5	I (3.76 ±0,3)	III (3.51 ±0.47)	V (3.19 ±0.5)	IV (3.35 ±0.25)	II (3.51 ±0.1)	
6-20	I (3.9 ±0.25)	III (3.51 ±0.3)	V (3.38 ±0.54)	IV (3.42 ±0.12)	II (3.6 ±0.2)	
>20	I (3.87 ±0.25)	IV (3.44 ±0.41)	V (3.32 ±0.37)	III (3.53 ±0,19)	II (3.59 ±0,18)	

Table 5. Distribution of types of value orientations in Belarusian teachers with various teaching experience (ranks, scores)

Types of value orientations

Pedagogical experience (years)	Pedagogical	Spiritual-moral	Life	Civil	Intellectual	Professional
0-5	I (3.81 ±0,42)	V (3.3 ±0,48)	II (3.48 ±0.5)	IV (3.41 ±0.49)	III (3.42 ±0.3)	
6-20	I (3.88 ±0,54)	IV (3.36 ±0,36)	V (3.28 ±0.55)	III (3.46 ±0.46)	II (3.49 ±0.38)	
>20	I (3.84 ±0,43)	IV (3.32 ±0,53)	V (3.32 ±0.6)	III (3.38 ±0.56)	II (3.51 ±0.48)	

Comparative analyses of social-professional valuable orientations dynamics manifestation in teachers of different generations revealed that such values (in scores) as Goodwill (4.1), Decency (4) and Sense of duty, Respect to themselves and others, Cheerfulness, Education and Tolerance (3.91 per each) are most realized in young Russian teachers' life; Decency (good manners, politeness) and Respect (to themselves and others) (4.13 per each) are inherent in teachers from Belarus.

Russian teachers with a pedagogical experience of 6-20 years manifest the following valuable orientations: Goodwill (4.27), Honesty (4.18), Mercy and Patriotism (4 scores each), Decency (3.91), Endurance and self-control (3.91) while Belarusian teachers display Mercy (4.53) and Decency (4).

In the hierarchy established according to the degree of values greatest realization in life, Communicativeness (4.27 scores out of 5 possible), Independence in planning and organization of their own activity and children's activity (4.18 scores), High demands and Mercy (4 scores per each), Decency (3.91), Self-possession and self-control (3.91) take the most place in Russian teachers-experts; Belarusian teachers manifest Decency and Honesty (4 scores each) in this case.

It is revealed that Russian teachers with pedagogical experience less than 20 years do not consider Ideological-political conviction, High demands and Social activity as quite valuable orientations. This attitude essentially changes with increasing experience since teachers having professional experience over 20 years are less guided by Economic independence, Enjoyment of nature beauty and Creativity manifestation. High demands are less appreciated values -means in Belarusian teachers throughout their professional career; professional teachers also add Social activity.

The degree of opinions' correlation in teachers with various pedagogical experience concerning the selection of social and professional values significance (terminal and instrumental values) has been confirmed by means of concordance coefficient. Average and high coherence of teachers' opinions in three groups of pedagogical experience is revealed, at $p \leq 0.05$:

in group of young teachers ($W_1=0.63$ and $W_2=0.79$ in Russian teachers and $W_1=0.75$ and $W_2=0.69$ in Belarusian teachers); in group of teachers with pedagogical experience of 6-20 years ($W_1=0.78$ and $W_2=0.83$, and also $W_1=0.73$ and $W_2=0.65$ for Russian and Belarusian teachers respectively); in group of teachers - experts ($W_1=0.75$ and $W_2=0.85$ in Russian teachers and $W_1=0.51$ and $W_2=0.63$ in Belarusian teachers).

Correlation analyses of links between values and value orientations in teachers with various pedagogical experience were conducted to obtain a more complete picture of peculiarities in the structure of teachers' value sphere; highly significant correlations between average and strong density of examined indicators ($p \leq 0.01$) were brought out.

Comparative analyses identified certain regularities in important social-professional values of studied teachers, namely: young Russian teachers distinguished Professional achievements and Social contacts from especially significant system-forming values (interaction with children, parents and colleagues); young Belarusians highlighted National sovereignty and Happy family life; Russian teachers – professionals specified Professional pedagogical ideals and Financially secured life and Belarusian teachers-professionals pointed out Intellectual property and Science; teachers-experts of Russia identified Social equality and Peaceful life while their Belarusian colleagues singled out National security and Innovations.

Social Activity is among fundamental determinants of social-professional value orientations in Russian teachers with less than 20 years of work experience; Social Justice is significant for teachers with over 20 years of pedagogical experience. Young Belarusian teachers and teachers - professionals refer Respect for Intellectual Property and Creative Activity to system-forming value orientations while teachers-experts specify Intellectual Activity and Charity.

Findings

Within the framework of our research, a social portrait of the average teacher was obtained on the basis of individual data. So, Russian teaching staff is represented by female teachers aged between 46 to 55 years, their teaching experience is over 20 years. The teaching staff of the Republic of Belarus is represented by women aged between 31 to 45 years with pedagogical experience of a bit over 20 years.

It has been established that Russian teachers of today are distinguished by the distribution of value types depending on the length of their pedagogical activity. Thus, professional values make up the dominant group of values (terminal values) in young teachers; spiritual and moral values are characteristic for experts with more than 5 years of pedagogical experience.

Belarusian teachers are guided by spiritual and moral values, regardless of their teaching experience.

In contrast to Russian teachers, Belarusian teachers refer intellectual values to the least significant values from the point of view of their vital principles throughout their professional development. In Russia, teachers having pedagogical experience up to 20 years mark out intellectual values as least important as well; teachers with experience over 20 years point out civil values.

A number of regularities in the distribution of values in teachers of the post-Soviet space with various pedagogical experience were identified. In particular, a significant individual variability was revealed in the group of life values in Russian teachers; on the contrary, the spread of individual values in the group of professional values is minimum.

Belarusian teachers with various pedagogical experience have revealed a somewhat different specificity in the value sphere, e.g. the greatest individual differences were found in the group of civil values, and insignificant individual variability is determined in the group of life values.

It is interesting to mention that in the sample of Russian teachers, young teachers unlike teachers with other work experience revealed a wider range of individual values in spiritual, moral and intellectual values. As for the Belarusian sample, a similar picture is typical for another age group - teacher-experts.

Let us note that Russian teachers with a pedagogical experience from 6 to 20 years and Belarusian teachers having over 20 years of experience evaluate the importance of many social-professional values as "quite important" and "extremely important" values more often than other educators..

Comparative analyses of the structure of teachers' valuable sphere in different cultures showed the following: Health (physical and mental) and Happy family life are key values of teachers in two cultures regardless of their professional activity experience. Besides, kindness is the value which does not lose its relevance for Russian teachers with various experience in their professional activity. Duration of pedagogical activity predetermines a number of features inherent in valuable sphere of Russian teachers. So, achievement of happiness as the greatest internal satisfaction with conditions of their life, wealth and meaningfulness of life, implementation of their human mission and active living position are important for young teachers; peaceful life is a significant value for teachers with experience; such achievements as happiness and peaceful life are significant for teachers having professional experience over 20 years.

Achievement of happiness is also important for Belarusian teachers – professionals, teachers experts' experience of their professional activity determines a valuable vector on Professional pedagogical ideals and Peaceful life.

The value of Public recognition is less recognized by both Russian and Belarusian teachers with various pedagogical experience. Moreover, working Russian teachers consider Intellectual property as least valuable; this value loses its consistency for teachers from Belarus with pedagogical experience over 5 years.

The analysis of instrumental values specified that teachers with various pedagogical experience, both in Russian and Belarusian samples, implement spiritual and moral values at most. Regardless of pedagogical experience, Russian teachers refer civil values to least significant ones as means to solve professional tasks. The similar picture is characteristic for Belarusian teachers, except young teachers for whom life valuable orientations are least preferable.

Distribution of other types of value orientations determines the equivalence of professional, life and intellectual instrumental values manifestation in educators of two cultures with various experience of pedagogical activity.

The greatest dispersion according to individual values in Russian young teachers is found in life and civil values; in civil values of professional teachers (work experience of 6-20 years); and in life values in teachers with experience over 20 years. Teachers in the Belarusian sample having various teaching experience, in comparison with the Russian sample, manifest insignificant individual variation in instrumental values distribution.

It is important to emphasize that Russian and Belarusian teachers choose ways and means to manifest their decency throughout their professional careers as a tool for achieving their goals.

Russian teachers with less than 20 years of experience refer benevolence to leading value orientations realized in their lives but teachers with more than 20 years of experience point out communicativeness. Teachers with profound pedagogical experience (over 20 years) manifest professional values and qualities to the greatest degree in comparison with teachers having other professional experience.

Young Belarusian teachers tend to demonstrate orientation towards respect for themselves and others, teachers-professionals manifest compassion and a caring attitude towards others, and teachers-experts-show their honesty.

On the basis of comparative analysis, it was revealed that system-forming social-professional terminal and instrumental values of Russian and Belarusian teachers, regardless of their teaching experience, are not considered as leading values for these teachers.

Only some leading values acting as guidelines in the life of Russian teachers with various professional experience have revealed coincidences with system-forming values, namely: for young teachers - Social contacts; for teachers - professionals - Professional pedagogical ideals; for teachers-experts - Peaceful life. As for Belarusian teachers, coincidences of system-forming values of the value sphere with dominant values were identified in young teachers in the value "Happy Family Life".

Conclusion

The conducted research revealed that social and professional values are formed and developed throughout the entire pedagogical activity. They act as unique life and *professional guidelines* at each professional stage of formation on the basis of which the teacher masters and carries out his/her pedagogical activity; moreover, they are also effective means that ensure professional growth of teacher's personal qualities and socially significant result of professional activity.

Teachers from Russia and Belarus with various pedagogical experience manifest dominant and system-forming social and professional values and value orientations. Proximity to the hierarchy of social-professional value orientations have been testified in Russian and Belarusian teachers.

Spiritual and moral values establish the basis of teachers' value sphere, regardless of nationalities and pedagogical experience; this proves the uniqueness of value basis in teachers' professional development as carriers and regulators of spiritual culture of society.

The value sphere of Belarusian teachers is less subject to change throughout their professional development in comparison with Russian teachers. A new vector of Russian society development determines the dynamics of value system formation in young teachers. Russian educators with a great pedagogical experience manifest professional values and qualities to the greatest degree in comparison with teachers having other professional experience and with Belarusian teachers as well.

Health and Happy Family Life are key guiding principles in the life of Russian and Belarusian teachers, regardless of their pedagogical experience. Achievement of personal happiness and peaceful life is of great importance for teachers in both cultures.

Intellectual value orientations in teachers of the studied countries occupy higher positions than intellectual values-goals. At the same time, intellectual property as the author's product of intellectual activity is not recognized by pedagogues of these countries as a necessary pedagogical value, therefore that, unfortunately, leads to unscrupulous use of intellectual labor at all stages of professional development.

The fact that Russian and Belarusian teachers realize the importance of their personality's influence on the formation of younger generation moral culture and focus to demonstrate their decency as a model of socially-recognized behavior throughout their professional careers is proved. At the same time, modern educators with various educational experience from Russia and Belarus devalue the importance of public recognition by others, including learners, and, consequently, teachers are not ready to occupy a leading position in the process of raising children and adolescents.

The structure of the value sphere of Russian and Belarusian teachers with various teaching experience has its own specificity. Due to obtained facts, it can be ascertained that some values are not fully understood by teachers; there is some discrepancy between declared and real values, and, therefore, it is important to develop a system to implement local incentives of interest in various categories of pedagogical workers so as to raise social and professional values.

Obtained research results allow us to specify perspective directions aimed to increase the efficiency of teachers' professional activity and retraining of highly qualified specialists considering the importance of their social and professional values for work in modern multicultural educational systems and to optimize ways of cross-cultural professional dialogue.

The study of value sphere of teachers from other post-Soviet countries and countries of the former socialist block is among promising areas for further scientific research on the topic in order to specify invariance and uniqueness of the value basis in teachers' professional development.

Acknowledgements

The work is performed according to the Russian Government Program of Competitive Growth of Kazan Federal University.

References

- Andreev, V.I., 2005. Pedagogy of higher education: an innovative-prognostic course. Center for Innovative Technologies, Kazan, p. 500.
- Barbashova, L.I., 2009. Development of teacher's value orientations as a condition for improving professional competence. PhD Thesis, St. Petersburg, p. 177.
- Bobneva, M.I., 1978. Social norms and behavior regulation. Science, Moscow, p. 312.
- Drobnitsky, O.G., 2002. Moral philosophy. Gardariki, Moscow, p. 523.
- Drozdikova-Zaripova, A.R., Kalatskaya, N.N., 2017. Cross-national examination of teachers' intercultural values, *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 237, p. 182.
- Fisher, W., 2013. The study of values: professional ethics of Israeli teachers, *Social psychology of education* 16 (2), p. 297.
- Ning, Hoi Kwan, Lee, Daphnee, Lee, Wing On, 2015. Relationships between teacher value orientations, collegiality, and collaboration in school professional learning communities, *Social Psychology of Education: An International Journal* 18, p. 337.
- Ilimkhanova, L., Perlenbetov, M., Tazhbayeva, S., Assylkhanova, M., Topanova, G., Sadvakassova, Z., Berdibaeva, S., Darhanova, A., 2014. The hierarchy of value orientations in Kazakhstan as the basis of national mentality, *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences* 5 (20), p. 2641.
- Şahin, S.A., Tunca, N., Altınkurt, Y., Yılmaz, R., 2016. Relationship between Professional Values and Critical Thinking Disposition of Science-Technology and Mathematics Teachers, *EURASIA Journal of Mathematics, Science & Technology Education* 12(1), p. 25.
- Trotskaya, A.I., 2015. Formation of social and professional values in future teachers of vocational training. PhD Thesis, Omsk, p. 245.
- Tselikkaya, T., Phyloglu, S., 2014. Personal attitudes of social sciences teachers in relation to values and values of education, *Educational Sciences: Theory and Practice* 14 (4), p. 1551.
- Tyrnova, O.A., 2010. Features of value orientations in modern youth, *Pedagogy and psychology of education* 3, p. 71.

- Vongkulluksn, V.W., Xie, K., Bowman, M.A., 2018. The role of value on teachers' internalization of external barriers and externalization of personal beliefs for classroom technology integration, *Computers and Education* 118, p. 70.
- Zeir, E.F., & Pavlova, A.M., 2008. Psychology of vocational education: practical work. Publishing Center "Academy", Moscow, p. 144.
- Petukhova, E. A., 2013. Professional-pedagogical values of the teacher: creativity, *News of the Altai State University* 2 (78), p. 68.
- Isaev, I.F., 2004. Professional-pedagogical culture of the teacher. Academy, Moscow, p. 207.
- Shiyanov, E.I., 1991. Humanization of pedagogical education: state and prospects. Stavropol, Moscow, p. 206.
- Ravkin, Z.I., 1995. Education development in Russia: new value guidelines, *Pedagogy* 5, p. 87.
- Korotaeva, E.V., Matveichuk E.N., 2012. Professional values of the teacher's profession: concepts and classifications, *Pedagogical education in Russia* 3, p. 11.
- Veugelers, W., 2010. Moral values in pedagogical education, *International Encyclopedia of Education* 7, p. 650.